

MODALSHIFT

D7.1 - DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

Multimodal Optimisation leveraging Data Acquisition from Local Stakeholders towards a Holistic Improvement of Freight and People Transport

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R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	X
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patent filings, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	
ETHICS	Deliverables related to ethics issues	
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	
OTHER	Software, technical diagrams, algorithms, models, etc.	

Dissemination level

PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in the CORDIS project's page)	X
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

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1 PROJECT ABSTRACT

The vision of **MODALSHIFT** lies in the creation of a transport network and traffic management optimisation framework, trusted and valuable for local stakeholders, that bridges the data from infrastructures, logistics and mobility operators.

New IoT devices - a smart box enabling Capacity-as-a-Service, and an e-subscription device for public transport access for vulnerable people, will increase the sources for data collection. A mobility data space, associated with novel geolocation data anonymisation, will be set up in the 3 Pilot Sites (Bulgaria, Italy, Spain) to ensure trusted and secure data exchange between data providers and users. This multisource data will enhance traffic state forecasting and increase the detection rate of events by 15%. On this basis, predictive and prescriptive analytics and synchro modality-based scenarios, tested in digital twins and early pilots, will identify optimal actions of transport stakeholders for adjusting their operations, towards a reduction of 25% of the interconnection or transshipment delays.

Agent-based modelling will identify how a modal shift towards low-carbon, active and shared mobility services can be acceptable by end-users and support a reshape of the public transport services and the use of urban space. A multimodal traffic management platform will orchestrate, within the data space, the cooperation of stakeholders at network and multimodal hub scales. It enables the integration of dynamic optimisation algorithms with operational drivers' tools for mobility operators, and of static models with a visual interface for transport planners. The determination of governance models, values for each stakeholder, dynamic pricing and business models will steer the participation of 8 stakeholders for each Pilot Site in the multimodal traffic management system.

With this approach, MODALSHIFT stimulates new uses of the transport network to reduce traffic congestion for low-carbon and inclusive mobility, avoiding pernicious rebound effects.

2 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan (DCEP) for MODALSHIFT describes the consortium's overarching strategy to communicate, disseminate, and exploit the project's results. It details the target audiences, main messages, activities, and strategies designed to overcome potential communication barriers and ensure wide and lasting impact. Based on the Work Plan structure, the document specifies tailored communication and dissemination needs, defines targeted audiences and objectives and identifies the key messages to be delivered to each audience. To reach these identified audiences, the channels and tools for sharing information on MODALSHIFT's activities will be explained. In addition, the DECP details how project results and outcomes will be exploited to maximise the project's impact, visibility, and sustainability beyond its lifetime. It includes methods to identify exploitation strategies, both during and after the project's lifetime, while monitoring impact and defining Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess the effectiveness and influence the project's DEC activities. Furthermore, the document proposes a risk mitigation plan addressing barriers that could hinder the project's communication and exploitation efforts. The plan is around a management section that provides an agenda of activities, detailed in the following sections, to organise and coordinate actions throughout the project's implementation. Finally, this document is intended to be a living document, updated as needed during the project's progress in response to emerging needs, opportunities, and stakeholder feedback.

2.1 PURPOSE

The DEC plan has several objectives. Among them are the presentation of the brand identity of the project, the establishment of a strategy for the project activities, the definition of the core values, key messages and goals for each target group. A list of the tools and communication channels used during the project will also be presented. Finally, this DCEP will define the primary audience of the MODALSHIFT project to ensure its long-term sustainability, even after its lifetime, through the dissemination of the results.

2.2 INTENDED AUDIENCE

This DCEP has for its destination the communication, dissemination and exploitation leaders, particularly the WP7 leaders, which includes all the partners of the MODALSHIFT consortium. At a larger scale, the DECP will influence the six target groups (cf. section 3) of the project defined in the project, being the transport network stakeholders, the logistics and freight value chain stakeholders, the mobility of people value chain stakeholders, the mobility users, the other international and national initiatives and the scientific community, and lastly the policy makers and public bodies. The DCEP will then indicate to the comm&diss leaders how to reach the target groups through the identification of their needs and the MODALSHIFT's objectives.

2.3 DESCRIPTION OF THE MAIN ACTIVITIES

The main activities carried out along the DECP are structured as follows:

- Design of the MODALSHIFT's brand identity: logo, EU acknowledgements, disclaimer, website, social media accounts and repositories chosen (cf. section 4).
- Communication campaign timetable summarising the following target group: the characteristics and communication needs, the communication objectives, examples of key messages and communication action & channels (cf. section 4.3.4).
- Promotional materials are defined as leaflets, roll-up banners, brochures, e-newsletters, and animated videos. This communication support will also be made available digitally (cf. section 4.5.1).
- Dedicated newsletter issued every 6 months, with content structure for upcoming deployment activities (cf. section 4.5.3).
- White papers and policy-oriented papers analysing relevant EU and national policy developments and regulatory gaps affecting multimodal transport optimisation (cf. section 4.5.4).
- Scientific dissemination, including gold open-access peer-reviewed publications in high-impact transport and mobility journals (cf. section 4.5.5).
- Engagement workshops, roundtables and conferences, often organised in local languages in the pilot site and presentation of the MODALSHIFT's project at national and international level events (e.g. **TRA, ITS Europe/World, Urban Mobility days, WCTR, ETC** and others) (cf. section 4.5.6).
- Joint initiatives synergies establishment with major EU transport projects and clusters. Also, collaboration opportunities agenda making with projects such as **FRONTIER, ORCHESTRA, TANGENT, DIT4Tram, DELPHI, SYNCHROMODE, AXUMEN** and **FEDORA**. Networking activities planning (cf. section 4.5.7).

These activities target broad visibility, consistent stakeholder engagement and strong policy and scientific impact to support long-term adoptions and exploitation of MODALSHIFT outcomes.

2.4 KEY RESULTS

The key results of this deliverable can be summarised as follows.

To reach its six main stakeholder groups, the DECP delivers a tailored communication and dissemination approach for each of them, ensuring each receives the specific evidence, benefits and engagement opportunities they need to support awareness, adoption and long-term impact.

Table 1: Communication characteristics depending on the target group

	Transport network stakeholders	Logistics & Freight value chain stakeholders	Mobility of people value chain stakeholders	Mobility users	Other international and national initiatives and the scientific community	Policy makers and public bodies
Needs	Operational efficiency, interoperability, and real-time coordination	Cost/time optimisation, regulatory clarity, business benefits	Integration of systems, improved service quality, and data sharing	Clear, accessible information demonstrating tangible benefits	Access to methods, open data, evidence, and open-source tools	Evidence-based insights for regulatory improvements and scaling
Key messages and focus	MODALSHIFT is improving multimodal traffic management and data exchange	MODALSHIFT is enabling savings by data-driven modal shift and freight optimisation	MODALSHIT is developing interoperable tools, enhancing planning and intramodality for passengers	MODALSHIFT is reducing delays in transport, is being inclusive, and is supporting low-carbon mobility	MODALSHIFT is a contributor to EU innovation & multimodal data ecosystems	MODALSHIFT presents policy recommendations supporting modal shift, resilience, and sustainability
Communication actions and channels	Participation in technical events (TRA, ITS), webinars, working groups, and ARB involvement	Participation in logistics fairs, targeted webinars (data anonymisation, optimisation), workshops	Participation in mobility-focused events, thematic webinars, and stakeholder workshops	Participation in co-creation workshops, local communications (posters/displays), and social media	Open-access publications, joint events, participation in CCAM, DTLF, and data space networks	Policy briefs, EU-level events (POLIS, CCAM), direct engagement

As for the communication campaign, it will follow the timeline below:

Figure 1: MODALSHIFT communication agenda

2.5 RESEARCH AND IMPLICATIONS

Through the establishment of a coherent, evidence-driven communication and dissemination architecture tailored to each of the six stakeholder groups, with specific and adequate messages.

The communication and dissemination, mapping, and stakeholder-specific analysis will enable the feeding of the different phases of the project. Indeed, future research priorities will be informed by early feedback collected through workshops, Advisory and Replication Board (ARB) interactions, and technical events. Problems and signals related to interoperability bottlenecks, regulatory constraints or user acceptance will help refine algorithms, data pipelines and use cases.

The DECP planning will also provide predictable content release, enabling the consortium to progressively validate assumptions and steer R&D activities towards validated needs. DECP's structure and implementation roadmap will finally accelerate the deployment of multimodal tools, thanks to well-informed operators and policy makers, and have a scalable impact as the project's contributions will become embedded in broader initiatives and data ecosystems and provide evidence-based communication.

2.6 POLICY IMPLICATION

All the results that will be highlighted by this DEC plan will provide guidelines for policymakers. The results of the DECP reveal important policy implications that can support ongoing EU efforts around sustainable mobility, data governance and multimodal transport integration. The policy makers will be strongly involved in the replication of the solutions and tools developed in Canada (partner in MODALSHIFT).

3 ABBREVIATIONS

Table 2: List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ARB	Advisory and Replication Board
B2B	Business-to-business
B2C	Business to Consumer
CS	Case Study
DECP	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan
EO	Expected Outcome
KER	Key Exploitation Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MTM	Multimodal Traffic Management
PR	Project Result
TEN-T	Trans-European Transport Network
TG	Target Group
WP	Work Package
MX	Month X
MAAS	Mobility-As-A-Service
CAAS	Capacity-As-A-Service

1 INTRODUCTION AND OBJECTIVES

The Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Plan (DECP) establish the strategic and operational framework for all dissemination, exploitation and communication activities within the MODALSHIFT project, implemented collaboratively by all project partners. The associated work package (WP7) is led by EQY, with strong and continuous collaboration from all consortium members. The overall strategy of the activities is documented in this deliverable.

Within WP7, the DECP serves as a guideline and harmonisation tool for all WPs' activities, ensuring a coherent strategy and appearance of tasks and deliverables across the project. The main objectives of this document are to provide:

- A unified brand image of the project,
- A consistent implementation strategy for project activities among all partners,
- Tools, communication channels, supporting materials, and guidelines for DEC,
- A coherent approach for engaging external stakeholders and target groups,
- A reference document that outlines the goals, core values, key messages, and content structure of project communications,
- A follow-up guide to disseminate correctly and effectively the results and events related to the project's sustainability,
- A clear guideline to ensure exploitation of the relevant results of the project.

The DECP will be reviewed and updated every six months, closely interacting with other work packages—particularly those generating results and policy recommendations — to revise activities according to ongoing activities and needs in terms of communication and dissemination. The updates will reflect both project progress and the experience gathered within MODALSHIFT, ensuring the communication and dissemination strategy remains effective and aligned with project objectives and stakeholder needs.

1.1 PROJECT OBJECTIVES AND EXPECTED IMPACTS

The overall objective of the MODALSHIFT project is to design, develop and test optimised network and traffic management services to support the uptake of sustainable and inclusive transport modes. The solutions developed, by bridging the mobility of freight and people, ensure secure and trusted data collection and exchange processes, and support the adoption by stakeholders. In particular, the project wants to offer ways of avoiding or reducing travel and encourage modal shift toward more sustainable models, then supporting sustainable urban mobility planning and the promotion of walking and cycling.

To do so, the project answers the expected outcomes (EO), as detailed in the Grant Agreement:

- Optimised multimodal transport network and traffic management, for efficient door-to-door mobility of passengers and freight (from producers to last mile deliveries) (EO1).
- Validated solutions for effective and secure data exchange across all modes of transport, for dynamic and responsive multimodal network and traffic management (EO2).
- Validated systems for accurate detection and resolution of network bottlenecks, improving safety, security, resilience and overall performance of the transport network, enabling proactive mobility management (EO3).
- New tools and services for optimising the mobility of passengers and freight, in cities and other areas, cutting traffic jams and improving multimodal traffic flows (EO4).
- Workable governance arrangements for multimodal transport network and traffic management, in view of further supporting regulatory and policy actions (EO5).

Building on these expected outcomes, the project anticipates a set of broader impacts that must be taken into account when designing adequate communication and dissemination materials. These **wider impacts** include:

- Optimised transport networks through improved detection and resolution of traffic bottlenecks, contributing to clean, accessible, and affordable multimodal mobility supported by upgraded and resilient physical (IoT) and digital infrastructures.
- Improved interconnectivity and efficiency across transport modes, promoting sustainable, smart, and integrated long-haul and regional freight transport and logistics.
- Reduced external costs, including congestion, traffic jams, Greenhouse Gas (GhG) emissions, and air and noise pollution of passenger mobility and freight transport, resulting in greater system-wide efficiency and resilience of both passenger mobility and freight transport.
- Strengthened local and regional capacities for governance, innovation, and coordination in passenger and freight transport, fostering the sustainable and efficient operation of multimodal transport networks.

1.2 CASE STUDIES

MODALSHIFT will demonstrate in WP5 the relevance and effective operation of the solutions developed by installing and operating them in 3 different pilot sites in Europe (Trieste, Madrid and Varna - Figure 2) for different applications.

Figure 2: Representation of the case studies and their readiness levels

Pilot site 1 – Italy - Port of Trieste

Trieste is an Italian municipality of 199.131 inhabitants located in the Northeast of Italy, a few kilometres away from the Slovenian border. The port of Trieste is a strategic location, being a crucial link in the European Trans-

European Transport Network (TEN-T) Mediterranean and Adriatic-Baltic corridors, which connect Austria and Slovenia with the main cities of the North Adriatic and Eastern Europe. Despite being a leading port for goods traffic and the first oil point of transition in the Mediterranean, the Trieste Port lacks interoperability between its several points of access: water, rail and road, leading to disruptions and delays as well as inferences in loading and unloading schedules. Also, the Port of Trieste still relies on ageing railway infrastructure, which will need to be upgraded to support efficient multimodal transport.

Pilot site 2 – Bulgaria - Municipality of Varna

The 1 million-inhabitant Bulgarian city is located on the Black Sea and has several key infrastructures and services in place, including a pedestrian area in the city centre and a well-established public transportation network with trains, buses and trolleybuses. However, urban mobility is lagging due to seasonality challenges and peak mobility demand in summer. Despite its ideal location for freight mobility, Varna still lacks boat transportation. Finally, the traffic light is still handled by a municipal company; the city's urban planning and modelling remain limited. A framework to integrate multimodal solutions into long-term urban planning is also missing.

Pilot site 3 – Spain – Madrid

Capital of Spain, Madrid, gathers 3.3 million people and covers an area of 605.77 km², expanding to 8.000 km² and not less than 69.7 million inhabitants for the metropolitan area. With such a population, Madrid has established an extensive suburban and interurban transport network to support the daily trips of commuters. Yet, as multiple modes of transportation converge (e.g. freight services and passenger transit), the communication system between the various stakeholders is not united, resulting in delays and disruptions in traffic (punctuality, reliability, user satisfaction and adoption). This goes along with a lack of synchro modality and no Capacity-as-a-service of freight in available public transport space, enabling thus interconnecting passenger and freight transportation.

2 COMMUNICATION, EXPLOITATION AND DISSEMINATION OVERALL STRATEGY

The communication, exploitation and dissemination strategy aims to precisely identify and define the primary audience of the MODALSHIFT project, ensuring that outreach activities are accurately tailored to ensure the sustainability of the project outcomes during and after the project lifetime.

- ◆ **The Communication** of the project: To share information about the project with a broad audience, raising public awareness of its objectives, activities and results.
- ◆ **The Dissemination** of the project: To share research results with the scientific community, as well as the industry, the civil society and the policy makers.
- ◆ **The Exploitation** of the project: To use the project's results for developing, creating, marketing or improving a product, a process, a service or shaping a policy.

2.1 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

The **WP 7 – communication, dissemination and networking** – is dedicated to the communication, dissemination and networking activities of the project to reach the identified target group of stakeholders and guarantee visibility of key project outputs, also after the end of MODALSHIFT.

It considers key groups of stakeholders, national and international initiatives, the scientific community, civil society organisations, and policymakers, with a focus on delivering targeted messaging that advances MODALSHIFT's goals (see section 3).

By encouraging sustainable mobility, raising awareness about modality shifts, and promoting innovation through collaborative initiatives, the project seeks to enhance cross-sector engagement. Special attention is given to involving scientific researcher communities to inspire cooperation and reflection on mobility issues, making the messaging impactful, and inviting active participation in sustainable transportation efforts.

The strategy also directs the choice of communication channels (see section 4) to maximise MODALSHIFT's reach, including knowledge-sharing events throughout Europe and beyond, especially Canada. It incorporates mechanisms to evaluate audience engagement and refine communication methods over time. Ultimately, this strategy supports MODALSHIFT's mission by delivering pertinent and effective messages to the right stakeholders, thereby fostering awareness and commitment to sustainable mobility.

2.2 EXPLOITATION

In MODALSHIFT, the **WP6 – Business models, exploitation and replicability** – is specifically dedicated to the exploitation of the project outcomes. It aims to identify the value of stakeholders to participate in a collaborative MTM (Multimodal Traffic Management) system, business models and dynamic incentives for limiting traffic jams and exploitation and regulatory outlines towards upscaling.

A preliminary identification of the Project Results (PRs) and subsequent Key Exploitation Results (KERs) is presented in section 5 and will be further refined in the framework of WP6, which starts at M10 (March 2026).

3 TARGET GROUPS AND KEY MESSAGES

A stakeholder mapping exercise was started during the project setting up of the project and further undertaken in the framework of **WP1 – Contextual analysis, pilot site definition and requirements**, to support the development and implementation of the MODALSHIFT Communication and Dissemination strategy. The mapping is presented in the following sections, along with the communication objectives, needs, actions and communication channels. It is also completed in **Del D1.1 – Plan for engaging stakeholders** - submitted at M4 (September 2025), which specifically maps the ecosystem of each Pilot Site local stakeholders.

Six target groups (TG) have been identified, each of them having unique communication requirements, which MODALSHIFT's C&D Manager addresses by defining clear communication objectives and implementing tailored actions through appropriate channels (see section 4) for maximum impact.

At the beginning of the project, messages will be of a more general nature to build the MODALSHIFT identity, create awareness of the project and its aims, and engage the relevant stakeholders. Additional messages tailored to each type of stakeholder will be developed to match their needs throughout the project while highlighting the main goals and outcomes of MODALSHIFT as described above.

3.1 TG1: TRANSPORT NETWORK STAKEHOLDERS

Transport network stakeholders include public and private transport network managers, operators and regulators in various areas of transport (rail, ground, maritime, waterways), as well as municipal agents for traffic light and infrastructure control. To have a good footprint in the project, the first level of stakeholders that we want to reach is the CS transport managers in Varna and Trieste. To anticipate the project's impact after its duration, we will reach out more broadly to transport network stakeholders from targeted cities and regions outside the project.

This target group will **benefit** from the solutions developed at different levels:

- **Optimised transport network:** Access to multimodal traffic management and transport data space tools using dynamic optimisation and analytics algorithms can directly improve traffic infrastructure control and transport data space.
- **Economic and urban planning opportunities:** By testing the developed solutions in each of the Case Studies (taking place in 3 different countries), results can help design governance schemes, dynamic incentives and leverage adapted business models. This can also give insights on a broader European and international scale.

The expected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be reached by the end of the project for this TG are summarised in Table 3. A summary of the communication campaign for TG1 is also included.

Table 3: Communication characteristics and performance indicator for a good impact level on TG1

Characteristics & Communication needs	Communication objectives	Examples of key messages	Communication actions & channels	KPI (indicator + value)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Includes multimodal node operators and infrastructure managers (ports, rail hubs, intermodal terminals). ◆ Need a clear understanding of the project's data interoperability, benefits for traffic management and operational efficiency. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ To raise awareness on MODALSHIFT solutions for seamless modal integration. ◆ To demonstrate how the project improves operational coordination and data interoperability. ◆ To encourage collaboration in testing and validating the system. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ MODALSHIFT enhances the efficiency and reliability of door-to-door mobility for both people and freight. ◆ Through secure, multimodal data exchange, MODALSHIFT enables real-time coordination and automated traffic management across transport modes. ◆ MODALSHIFT's tools detect and resolve network bottlenecks, ensuring smoother 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Targeted fairs and events on transport (e.g. Transport Research Arena, ITS European/World Congress and CCAM (RTR conference)). ◆ Participation in Traffic Management and Modelling WGs in ECTRI and MTM Cluster. ◆ Technical webinar on MTM. ◆ Involvement through ARB. ◆ Online channels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Number of events targeting TG1 > 5 ◆ Number of webinars organised in the national language of all 3 pilot sites > 1 ◆ Number of EU-wide webinars with participation of TG1 actors >1 EU-wide webinar and > 15 participants from TG1

		<p>operations and reducing delays.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Dynamic data management ensures interoperability and integration of legacy systems, fostering scalable deployment across Europe. 		
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3.2 TG2: LOGISTICS AND FREIGHT VALUE CHAIN STAKEHOLDERS

Freight and logistics operators include B2B (business-to-business) and B2C (business-to-consumer), but also cargo bike fleet managers. Industrials and local stores are also integrated into the value chain. Based on the MODALSHIFT network (partners' operators), the consortium will focus on railway, maritime, ground freight operators, TMT terminal and other shunting operators, retailers and local stores known to the CS network. In a second part, logistics and freight stakeholders from cities and regions not involved in the project will be targeted.

This target group will **benefit** from the developed solutions at different levels:

- **Operational efficiency:** Access to innovative fleet management tools can optimise routes, monitor vehicles and reduce congestion time as well as delays. The development of dynamic pricing models can help balance demand and supply in freight services. Capacity-as-a-service smart box can improve coordination between logistics actors.
- **Compliance and protection of data:** Data anonymisation technologies can enable the sharing and use of data safely, in line with EU data regulations (GDPR, Data Act, etc.).

The expected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be reached by the end of the project for this TG are summarised in Table 4. A summary of the communication campaign for TG2 is also included.

Table 4: Communication characteristics and performance indicator for a good impact level on TG2

Audience (Target Group)	Characteristics & Communication needs	Communication objectives	Examples of key messages	Communication actions & channels	KPI
TG2: Logistics and freight value chain stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Freight and logistics operators, industrials, local suppliers and service providers. ◆ Need efficiency, real-time data, and regulatory compliance, but also business. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ To showcase the benefits of data-driven modality shifts in freight logistics. ◆ To promote the cost, time, and emission savings. ◆ To stimulate adoption and pilot participation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ MODALSHIFT enhances the efficiency and reliability of door-to-door mobility for both people and freight. ◆ Through secure, multimodal data exchange, MODALSHIFT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Events (e.g. Transport Logistic, Green Logistics Expo). ◆ Topical webinars (anonymisation of data, freight optimisation) with e.g. ID4M and ALICE network. ◆ ARB and local workshops. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Number of local workshops organised with the participation of TG2 stakeholders > 5 ◆ Number of TG2 stakeholders' members of

			<p>enables real-time coordination and automated traffic management across transport modes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ MODALSHIFT's tools detect and resolve network bottlenecks, ensuring smoother operations and reducing delays. ◆ Dynamic data management ensures interoperability and integration of legacy systems, fostering scalable deployment across Europe. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Online channels. 	<p>each local board > 5</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Number of webinars organised in each CS language > 1 ◆ Number of EU-wide webinars with TG2 actors > 1 ◆ EU-wide webinar with > 20 TG2 actors
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3.3 TG3: MOBILITY OF PEOPLE VALUE CHAIN STAKEHOLDERS

Mobility of people value chain stakeholders include suburban train operators, port authority, bike station installers, bus companies, carsharing app developers and public transport managers. First, the CS will focus on reaching the stakeholders present in the Madrid and Varna case studies. In the second part, the CS will expand the audience to reach mobility stakeholders from cities and regions not involved in the project.

This target group will **benefit** from the developed solutions at different levels:

- **Improved service efficiency:** The integration of AI-based predictive tools can optimise schedules, reduce congestion and adapt to real-time demand. Also, the centralised services developed throughout the project can enhance intermodally by connecting buses, bikes, trains and carsharing.
- **Local economic and environmental impact:** The collaboration between local operators, cities and innovation clusters participates in the promotion of green jobs and sustainable growth. Also, the developed solutions contribute to reducing CO2 emissions while promoting shared mobility.

The expected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be reached by the end of the project for this TG are summarised in Table 5. A summary of the communication campaign for TG3 is also included.

Table 5: Communication characteristics and performance indicator for a good impact level on TG3

Audience (Target Group)	Characteristics & Communication needs	Communication objectives	Examples of key messages	Communication actions & channels	KPI
<p>TG3: Mobility of people value chain stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Suburban train, freight and buses operators, carsharing app developers, and public transport managers. ◆ Need clarity on system interoperability and citizen benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ To promote the use of MODALSHIFT solutions to improve service planning and intermobility for passengers. ◆ To foster partnerships for pilot testing and data exchange. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ MODALSHIFT enhances the efficiency and reliability of door-to-door mobility for both people and freight. ◆ Through secure, multimodal data exchange, MODALSHIFT enables real-time coordination and automated traffic management across transport modes. ◆ MODALSHIFT's tools detect and resolve network bottlenecks, ensuring smoother operations and reducing delays. ◆ Dynamic data management ensures interoperability and integration of legacy systems, fostering scalable deployment across Europe. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Targeted events on mobility of people backed by the clusters ID4M and INNOVEE. ◆ Topical webinars. ◆ Involvement through ARB and local stakeholder workshops. ◆ Online channels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Number of TG3 stakeholders' members of each local board > 5 ◆ Number of local workshops organised with the participation of TG3 stakeholders > 3 local workshops including > 5 TG2 participants ◆ Number of webinars organised in each CS language > 1 ◆ Number of EU-wide webinars with TG3 actors > 1 EU-wide webinar with > 20 TG3 actors

3.4 TG4: MOBILITY USERS

Mobility users comprehend inhabitants and tourists. Particularly, the focus will be on public transport users and vulnerable groups (elderly, low-income and reduced mobility, etc.). The mobility users from the pilot site territories will be the first to be reached, while for the second part, the CS will extend to associations in regions not involved in the project.

This target group will **benefit** from the developed solutions at different levels:

- **Improved multimodal mobility:** Access to multimodal low-carbon shared/active mobility and delivery can reduce the door-to-door travel time of mobility users.
- **Multimodality design:** Participation *via* surveys and co-creation sessions on public transport design and needs enables mobility users to be actors in their mobility preferences and shape the urban modality of their environment.

The expected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be reached by the end of the project for this TG are summarised in Table 6. A summary of the communication campaign for TG4 is also included.

Table 6: Communication characteristics and performance indicator for a good impact level on TG4

Audience (Target Group)	Characteristics & Communication needs	Communication objectives	Examples of key messages	Communication actions & channels	KPI
TG4: Mobility users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Inhabitants, tourists, public transport users and vulnerable groups. ◆ Need accessible, non-technical information showing benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ To increase public awareness of sustainable transport options. ◆ To encourage behavioural change towards modality shift. ◆ To build trust around data privacy and ethical use. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ MODALSHIFT aims to decrease average travel delays for vulnerable users. ◆ By improving public transport service quality, passengers will experience greater reliability and satisfaction. ◆ MODALSHIFT fosters a seamless and inclusive travel experience, reducing stress, waiting times, and uncertainty during 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Co-creation workshops with representative local associations and citizens, focus groups and interviews/surveys. ◆ Representative EU-scale associations involved in ARB. ◆ Posters/displays in bus stops and multimodal hubs (e.g. Madrid Estacion Sur, Varna train station). ◆ Social media (and website). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Number of mobility users per use case involved in Local Actors Boards > 5 ◆ Number of mobility users per use case, answering dedicated surveys on user satisfaction > 1000 ◆ Overall user satisfaction level through surveys and opinion polls > 90%

			multimodal trips. ♦ The project will surely enable environmental benefits as it will optimise mobility trips and ensure low-carbon transport use.		
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The KPIs regarding the TG4 will be measured through the pilot site’s partners (ADF, PNAEAS, AVANZA, VARNA). Also, ID4M, as the partner involved in the setting-up and follow-up of the 3 pilot sites, will participate in the reaching of the indicators. The ethics committee board and advisory & replication board will also be involved in this process.

To do so, attendance sheets will be collected at each local pilot site meeting. Digital forms will also be envisaged as another option to evaluate mobility users' involvement. The online surveys will include an identification/specification of respondents’ categories for this purpose. The overall satisfaction will be ensured through dedicated validation questionnaires, Net-Promoter-Score (NPS) variants or opinion polls.

3.5 TG5: OTHER INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL INITIATIVES AND THE SCIENTIFIC COMMUNITY

The participants targeted include universities and research centres with strong networks, but also similar projects and initiatives (e.g. CCAM, C-ITS and EU Joint Undertaking clusters). The focus will be on the stakeholders inside the consortium, meaning the CCAM, CIVITAS, standardisation committees in the partner’s network, and EU research centres active on multimodal transport network optimisation.

This target group will **benefit** from the developed solutions at different levels:

- **Scientific innovation:** Optimisation algorithms, resolution of congestion techniques and dynamic incentives development are a fostering ground for scientific innovation, adding knowledge to the scientific community.
- **Replicability:** MODALSHIFT methods can be reused in other contexts, projects, or geographical areas, extending MODALSHIFT’s impact beyond the consortium and its use cases. Public datasets, deliverables, best practices, and recommendations enable replication sites to have guidelines.

The expected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be reached by the end of the project for this TG are summarised in Table 7. A summary of the communication campaign for TG5 is also included.

Table 7: Communication characteristics and performance indicator for a good impact level on TG5

Audience (Target Group)	Characteristics & Communication needs	Communication objectives	Examples of key messages	Communication actions & channels	KPI
TG5: International initiatives and the	♦ CCAM, deployEMDS, MTM Cluster, transport	♦ To position MODALSHIFT within the EU	♦ The project contributes to the CCAM and Data	♦ Sharing of best practices, joint scientific	♦ Number of views on publicly available datasets/deliverables > 200

<p>scientific community</p>	<p>optimisation workers.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Need scientific and technical outcomes, interoperability insights, and open data results, as well as open-source code and open methodologies. 	<p>innovation landscape.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ To foster knowledge exchange and synergy within related initiatives. ◆ Disseminate scientific results and best practices. 	<p>Space for Smart Mobility ecosystems, ensuring scientific and technical excellence in multimodal data management</p>	<p>publications. Active contribution to CCAM, Common EU mobility Data Space and DTLF events.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Gold open-access publications in high-impact journals (e.g. Transportation Research). ◆ Participation in events gathering logistics and mobility research communities, e.g. ITS European Congress, the ITF 2025 Summit, International Summit on electric and smart transportation (CA). ◆ Online channels (incl. newsletter, website). ◆ Direct contact with projects for joint events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Number of conference participations > 10 ◆ Number of CCAM event participations per year > 1 ◆ Number of scientific/technical papers submitted > 10 including > 4 joint publications ◆ Number of collaborative events gathering various EU projects and initiatives participating > 2
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To effectively measure these KPIs, the communication and dissemination work package leader (EQY), data collection and curation partners (UTAC, OCTO, GGI, NGS) and the coordinator (ITA) will oversee this task.

To do so, analytics dashboards will be used to evaluate deliverables and dataset consultation. As for events participation and papers publication, the Dissemination and Communication tracker (Excel document), already at the disposal of the partners, will be used. The planned dissemination activities tracker will complement the D&C tool.

3.6 TG6: POLICY MAKERS AND PUBLIC BODIES

Among **policy makers and public bodies**, we can distinguish policy makers at various levels that have a direct influence on transport regulations. They are split into two categories. Firstly, EU and national officials involved in CCAM and EU mobility DS, ISO/IEC, municipalities, public organisations and the Quebec government. On a superior level, supra-national regulators and policy makers will be targeted.

- **Evidence-based policymaking:** Testing developed solutions in case studies enables social acceptability pathways across the EU and the fostering of regulatory evolutions on a wider scale. Also, it offers the implementation of guidelines and regulatory frameworks for the scaling and uptake of transport, infrastructure, and mobility solutions.
- **Alignment with EU strategies:** the overall objective and activities of the project are aligned with the EU Green Deal, Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy, as well as the Data strategy (protection of the data).

The expected Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to be reached by the end of the project for this TG are summarised in Table 8. A summary of the communication campaign for TG6 is also included.

Table 8: Communication characteristics and performance indicator for a good impact level on TG6

Audience (Target Group)	Characteristics & Communication needs	Communication objectives	Examples of key messages	Communication actions & channels	KPI
TG6: Policy makers and public bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Municipalities, regional authorities, national ministries, and EU bodies. ◆ Need evidence-based results to guide transport, environmental, and data policies and environmental benefits. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ To provide decision support project findings. ◆ To influence policy frameworks supporting modality shifts and data interoperability. ◆ To foster replication and scaling at the EU level. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ MODALSHIFT redefines the transport network in a “vision and validate” paradigm, supporting evidence-based policymaking and adaptive regulation. ◆ MODALSHIFT creates body-centred governance models and policy guidelines for multimodal management for a more inclusive, efficient and resilient transport system. ◆ MODALSHIFT’s solutions reduce 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Policy briefs and recommendations (D6.2). ◆ Diffusion through available channels such as CCAM, Mobility Data Space and direct contact of relevant organisations. ◆ Policy-related events: Polis Conference, CCAM events, EU (clustering) events. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Number of policy briefs and recommendations publicly available: 3 ◆ Number of participants in CCAM events per year and at the Polis Conference > 1 ◆ Number of publications in policy-oriented journals > 3

			<p>congestion and emissions in multimodal hubs through synchro modal strategies, supporting the EU's Green Deal and Sustainable Urban Mobility goals while making car mobility more attractive.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ By reducing average interconnection times and reaction times to delays (e.g. late trains or vessels), MODALSHIFT improves network resilience and public service reliability. ◆ MODALSHIFT is accelerating the modal shift, transforming mobility habits, improving everyday transport and optimising the network. 		
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4 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS

4.1 MODALSHIFT IDENTITY

To communicate and disseminate the important information and project results of MODALSHIFT, Euroquality created a **brand identity** and **Comm&Diss toolkit of the project** - regularly updated and completed - available to all partners on a secured shared platform (detailed in D8.1 – Project Management Plan).

This toolkit includes: the MODALSHIFT logos, the graphic charter, different templates including PowerPoint presentation templates, deliverables, milestones and other working documents (word templates, posters, flyers and roll-ups). To facilitate their dissemination to the local population of the pilot sites, communication materials will be translated into local languages by the local partners.

4.1.1 MODALSHIFT LOGO

The visual and written identity of the MODALSHIFT project is a unique hallmark, designed for consistent use across all dimensions of the project, including communication and dissemination materials, both online and offline media outlets, project deliverables, and any other visual or written representation of the project and its components. It enables easy public recognition and ensures a coherent representation supported by all project partners (logo, colours, fonts, typefaces, images, other materials).

Figure 3: MODALSHIFT Logo (horizontal and round versions)

4.1.2 EU ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS AND DISCLAIMER

The following EU emblem (Figure 4) and disclaimer will be included in all deliverables and public documents, showing that MODALSHIFT is funded by the European Union’s HORIZON EUROPE Program.

Horizontal

Funded by
the European Union

Vertical

Funded by
the European Union

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Figure 4: EU acknowledgement and disclaimer

4.2 PROJECT WEBSITE

The website (<https://modalshift.eu/>, which will be launched end of **November 2025**) acts as a central knowledge hub for updates, reports, news, and consortium activities (Figure 5). It will engage the public, showcase pilot sites,

replicability sites and regional initiatives, and be used to connect the visitors with related EU and international programs.

The language of the website is English, and the pages featuring the pilot sites will also be available in local languages (Italian, Spanish and Bulgarian).

Figure 5: Homepage of the MODALSHIFT website (M6 - November 2025)

Materials developed for physical dissemination (i.e., leaflets, videos, infographics) will also be accessible in the “News” section of the website.

The MODALSHIFT website strategy is described in the following.

- **Who is sending the message?**

The website will act as the official communication channel of the project. The key messages (listed in section 3) will be sent on behalf of the MODALSHIFT project, represented jointly by EQY (the leader of the communication and dissemination Work Package), ITA (the coordinator), the work package leaders and the use case partners.

EQY is the one responsible for creating the website content based on the inputs of the partners. Technical content will therefore be checked by the WP leaders.

- **Who is the target?**

The website will address the **six stakeholder groups** identified with specific information needs:

1. **Transport network operators** such as traffic managers and infrastructure operators.
2. **Logistics and freight value chain stakeholders**, such as carriers, terminals and SMEs.
3. **Passenger mobility ecosystem**, such as public transport operators, Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) providers.

4. **End-users and mobility users**, such as citizens and local communities.
5. **Scientific community and related initiatives**, such as researchers, EU cluster projects and data scientists.
6. **Policy makers and public authorities**, such as the EU, national, regional and municipal authorities.

Beyond these stakeholders, the website's purpose will be to attract non-expert audiences by vulgarising the technical content, offering an interactive platform with infographics and insisting on the key role of the project in the environmental transformation.

- **What are the key messages?**

Based on the maturity level of the target groups, the website will present different types of content as introductory materials, technical updates based on Work Plan progression, pilot sites advancements, news and press releases, but also communication supports and materials.

The key messages will be inspired by the target group's key messages list (see section 3), but more broadly, it will be based on:

“Modalshift addresses the need for new ways of travelling—especially for short- to medium-distance journeys—designed to minimise carbon footprints in accordance with recent CO₂ emission agreements.”

- **What channels will be used?**

The MODALSHIFT website will be strongly linked to other social media and communication channels.

The website content will then be amplified by LinkedIn. The newsletter will also refer to the website as well as Instagram through reels formats.

- **What are the objectives?**

Statistical data will be gathered about the website visitors, the number of clicks, countries, etc. This data will be monitored using **Google Analytics Software**, and key metrics will be analysed to gain insights into the website's performance. Traffic sources, page views and average session duration will be assessed to optimise content and format. The website is adapted for many types of devices, such as desktop computers, tablets, and mobile phones.

Similarly, as for social media performance evaluation, a KPI of **3,000 visits per year** on the MODALSHIFT website has been set for an excellent impact on the public. Year-on-year growth in traffic is expected (+10%). In addition, at least **6 major updates** on the website per year will be made according to the communication timeline.

- **What are the expectations?**

The website will aim to generate progressive engagement (**Awareness → Interest → Engagement → Adoption**). This platform will be a gateway to adoption, not just information. Expected outcomes include behavioural change among mobility users, operational change among freight and transport managers, policy change through understanding of barriers and opportunities, but also data-driven recommendations, and market interest in technologies developed.

4.3 SOCIAL MEDIA

MODALSHIFT will leverage platforms like LinkedIn and Instagram to share news, promote campaigns, and foster interaction. Partners will use prescribed hashtags from the brand guide to unify social media presence.

4.3.1 LINKEDIN

- LinkedIn link access: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/modalshift-project/>

Figure 6: MODALSHIFT LinkedIn header page

To increase the awareness of the project on LinkedIn and enhance the impact of the communication, access rights to the project's LinkedIn account administrator page will be granted progressively to each partner organisation, as each organisation and its role in the project are introduced during the first communication campaign (see section 4.3.4).

The MODALSHIFT LinkedIn strategy will be the following.

- **Who is sending the message?**

On LinkedIn, several actors are expected to publish posts. On the MODALSHIFT LinkedIn page, EQY, as the communication leader, will create and post impactful messages under the WP leaders' validation. Consortium partners will then reshare the posts to expand reach.

Consortium partners are also expected to post on their own LinkedIn company page about the MODALSHIFT project on their task advancement. The other way around, the MODALSHIFT LinkedIn webpage will reshare these publications.

The strategy of resharing will ensure that different target groups are reached.

Professional tone will be used, and evidence-based content, aligned with other EU innovation initiatives, will be displayed.

- **Who is the target?**

LinkedIn will be used to reach professional, institutional and EU scientific communities' audiences.

The primary targets are:

1. **B2B/Technical:** transport network operators, logistics and freight stakeholders, public transport operators and MaaS developers
2. **Policy governance:** local, regional, national and EU policy makers, funding bodies, public authorities and EU agencies
3. **Science, innovation, industry:** researchers, innovation clusters, data space initiatives, sister projects (CCAM, MTM, POLIS, ALICE)

4. **Partner's network:** colleagues, urban mobility stakeholders
 5. **Secondary:** Journalists focused on transport and digital innovation, tech providers and start-ups, and end-users interested in sustainable mobility
- **What are the key messages?**

The key messages that will be displayed through LinkedIn are categorised as follows:

Transport networks

“MODALSHIFT is improving multimodal traffic management, interoperability, and real-time coordination.”

Logistics and freight

“Data-driven optimisation, time/cost savings, and better modal-shift decisions.”

Passenger mobility

“Integrated tools improving service planning, intramodality, and passenger experience.”

Scientific community

“Open data, open-source tools, shared methodologies, and validated pilot site evidence.”

Policy makers

“Trusted evidence to guide regulation, support multimodal data governance, and scale modal shift.”

General EU narrative

“MODALSHIFT delivers real-world demonstrations of how digital innovation accelerates the transition to sustainable, resilient, low-carbon mobility across Europe.”

- **What channels will be used?**

The LinkedIn strategy will use a mix of different types of posts and amplification channels.

Types of posts:

Project updates on milestones, deliverables and achievements.

Pilot sites snapshots through preliminary results, pictures, and testimonials.

Short videos and infographics.

Policy-focused posts on EU mobility priorities, link to policy briefs and actualities.

Behind-the-scenes content such as consortium meetings, workshops and events.

“Did you know?” educational posts.

Technical insights from WP leaders.

Interviews with technical leaders and stakeholders.

Consortium partners spotlights.

Reposts of relevant EU events & cluster news.

Collaboration callouts through sister projects, EU networks, etc.

These posts' impact will be expected to be amplified through reposts from partners' organisations, pilot sites stakeholders, LinkedIn groups and EU clusters.

- **What are the objectives?**

Over the 3-year lifespan of the project, KPIs of 2-3 posts per month will be achieved. At least **2,000 impressions per post** are expected, along with a 10% engagement rate. **Year-on-year traffic growth** is also expected (+10%).

- **What are the expectations?**

Like the MODALSHIFT website, the LinkedIn webpage is expected to bring awareness and progressive engagement. Professional engagement through increased interactions with transport operators, freight stakeholders, urban mobility authorities and EU networks. But also, scientific and technological engagement based on data frameworks and interoperability.

Finally, visibility on policymakers and engagement with regulatory bodies ahead of the project’s policy recommendations is envisioned. Generally, reputation building is a key aspect of LinkedIn, leveraging MODALSHIFT as a reference project for resilience of transport networks and urban mobility.

An overview of LinkedIn’s posts agenda is available in the figure below (cf. Figure 7).

Figure 7: LinkedIn's post publication agenda

4.3.2 INSTAGRAM

- Instagram link access: https://www.instagram.com/modalshift_project/

Figure 8: MODALSHIFT Instagram header page

The communication timeline agenda on Instagram will follow a similar timeline to LinkedIn. However, the objective through Instagram will be to reach a broader audience than on LinkedIn, in particular a non-expert and young audience (*17-30 years old*).

The subject of the post will then be accorded to the ones on LinkedIn but presented differently. For instance, the reels format will be chosen, allowing presentation of pieces of information animatedly, in a storyteller format.

On the frequency of the post, **2 posts per week** and **1 reel per month** will be put in place.

4.3.3 GUIDELINES FOR THE USE OF THE SOCIAL MEDIA ACCOUNTS

The responsibility for the popularity and impact of the posts will be on all the MODALSHIFT partners. Sharing through their existing network (e-mail, social media, newsletter, *etc.*), this should expectably be a way for them to reach the relevant stakeholders and beyond.

To effectively communicate throughout our social media channels, we defined and during the hashtags and tags to use, enabling us to reach interested communities as well as the EU scientific community and beyond.

4.3.3.1 Hashtags to use on social media (CINEA and Horizon Europe mention)

◆ Urban mobility hashtags

#HorizonEurope #EU #HorizonEU #EUFunded #EUProjects
#Transport #SustainableMobility #TransportManagement
#MissionCities
#ResearchAndInnovation #EUGreenDeal, #HorizonEurope #TransportResearch #SmartMobility
#DataInnovation #Cybersecurity #CCAM #Multimodality #Innovation #SustainableMobility
#Multimodality #TransportManagement #EUprojects #ResearchAndInnovation

◆ European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA) & initiatives on social media

LinkedIn – tag by using @ [CINEA - European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency](#)
@ [Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster](#)

Instagram – tag by using @EU_Science

◆ Project Officer of MODALSHIFT – Thiago TAVARES – on social media

LinkedIn – tag by using @Thiago Tavares (<https://www.linkedin.com/in/thiagojt/>)

4.3.4 COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGNS

All along the project, results and deliverables will be shared with the public on social media. Main findings with accessible visuals (infographics, fact sheets) and scientific publications with an open-access link will be the essential content published through LinkedIn and Instagram. One reel each six months will be published on Instagram to reach a broader and younger audience.

The estimated KPI set to reflect good reachability of all target groups and the public is set at ~20 posts per year on social media.

Regular communication campaigns will be launched throughout the project to communicate on the project activities, gathering, developments, progress, partners and events. The messages published will highlight the following:

- ◆ General presentation of the project (at the same time as the Kick-off meeting)
- ◆ Partners involved presentation
- ◆ Solutions developed presentation
- ◆ Work Packages presentation
- ◆ Use cases presentation
- ◆ Results and publication of deliverables/milestones
- ◆ Events attended
- ◆ Project impact on the local population

The preliminary timeline is as follows:

Table 9: Timetable for main social media campaigns

Period	Objectives	Key Content	Main partners involved	Communication support
June-Nov. 2025	Project Overview, introduction of the consortium and its vision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ General presentation of the project ◆ Partners involved presentation ◆ ARB presentation 	EQY, ITA	Infographics, short video presentation, and text
Dec. 2025 – May 2026	Explain the project's structure and early progress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Work packages presentation ◆ Solutions developed presentation ◆ Event coverage 	EQY, WP leaders, technology partners	Infographics, photos and text
June 2026 – Nov. 2026	Show the project's practical implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Use cases presentation ◆ Preliminary results 	ALL	Pictures, partners' quote, maps, infographics and text
Dec. 2026 – May 2027	Use cases progress on implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Interviews or testimonials from researchers and users involved ◆ Short "Did you 	EQY, Use cases leaders, ID4M	Pictures, partners' quotes, infographics and text

		know?" posts ♦ Events coverage		
June 2027 – Nov. 2027	Show the project's societal, economic, or environmental benefits	♦ Project impact on the local population ♦ Local engagement posts ♦ Cross-promotion with other EU projects (Sister project, Cluster)	EQY, ITA, AVANZA, ADF, VARNA	Pictures, video, partner's quote, community feedback, and text
Dec. 2027 – May 2028	Summarise achievements and ensure long-term visibility	♦ Results summary ♦ Project wrap-up video ♦ Final event summary and main outcomes ♦ Post-project continuation	ALL	Pictures, videos, infographics, partners' quotes/interviews, text
June 2028 – Nov. 2028	Ensure post-project uptake and highlight long-term exploitation & policy relevance	♦ Pilot site adoption stories/interviews ♦ Exploitation pathways ♦ Policy recommendations and alignment with EU mobility strategies ♦ Open tools, datasets and lessons displaying ♦ Announcements of follow-up initiatives	ALL + external stakeholders	Pictures, short videos, infographics, policy briefs extracts, partners' quotes, testimonials and text

4.4 SCIENTIFIC RESOURCE STORAGE PLATFORMS

4.4.1 ZENODO

To comply with the Open Access obligations of the project and enhance the dissemination of the project outputs, all public deliverables and publications will be available on the Zenodo MODALSHIFT community of the project (<https://zenodo.org/communities/modalshift/>). The community is part of the **EU Open Research Repository**, allowing long-term and open access to publications and data.

Multimodal Optimisation leveraging Data Acquisition from Local Stakeholders towards a Holistic Improvement of Freight and people Transport ✓

MODALSHIFT creates a trusted transport optimisation framework linking mobility, logistics, and infrastructure data. Using IoT, data spaces, and...

Part of [EU Open Research Repository](#)

Project <https://modalshift.eu> Instituto Tecnológico de Aragón and 15 more organizations

Figure 9: MODALSHIFT Zenodo community page

4.4.2 GITHUB

To publish, share, store or work together on code, concerned partners involved in data and AI-based algorithms for decision making (e.g. Tellae) will use a GitHub repository. The relevant links used during the project by the different teams will be made publicly accessible after the end of the project.

GitHub is implied in the long-term sustainability of the project, allowing the R&D community to continue to leverage the project after its end and to replicate it to possibly other geographical areas.

4.5 COMMUNICATIONS AND DISSEMINATIONS MATERIALS & ACTIVITIES

4.5.1 PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

To promote MODALSHIFT at conferences and events, project partners will create and use promotional materials. These materials will provide general project information, early technical and non-technical results, and calls to action. The suite of materials will include:

- Leaflets distributed at conferences by attending partners, with one leaflet issued mid-project to share initial results. The leaflet is the primary tool to reach local stakeholders at demonstration sites, highlight the project's international scope, and engage national and transnational audiences (see example Figure 10).
- Roll-up banners and brochures to support stakeholder recruitment, which will be translated into local languages by partners responsible for pilot sites (see examples Figure 11, Figure 12 and Figure 12).
- E-newsletters produced at appropriate intervals to communicate project progress and interim findings.
- An animated video presenting the project's aims, concept, and anticipated impacts, scheduled for release around Month 6. Other videos will be published throughout the project, explaining the technical concepts discussed during consortium meetings and making key concepts of the Horizon Europe MODALSHIFT project more accessible.

All promotional materials will be available electronically on the MODALSHIFT website for partners to download and share, while printable versions will be uploaded to a secure shared folder accessible to all MODALSHIFT partners for physical distribution. Throughout the project, the printing of the communication materials will be limited for environmental reasons.

Figure 10: Leaflets describing the project and the pilot sites

Figure 11: Roll-ups for the local-kick-off meetings in pilot sites' languages (Spanish and Italian)

MODALSHIFT
Multimodal Optimisation leveraging Data Acquisition from Local Stakeholders towards a Holistic Improvement of Freight and People Transport

Два приложни случая

1 Нисковъглероден градски превоз на товари чрез оптимизация на товарните велосипеди
Разполагане на сензори на велосипедите и въвеждане на система за проследяване и мониторинг в комбинация с модел за споделяне, ориентиран към Ногеса, на принципа „плащане за ползване“.

2 Подобряване на общественя транспорт и активната мобилност
Адаптиране на графиците/услугите на общественя транспорт и активната мобилност към сезонните модели на търсене и предстоящото развитие на велосипедните алеи

ЦЕЛИ

- Да се подобри устойчивата градска мобилност и да се намали задръстването във Варна чрез укрепване на нисковъглеродната логистика, подобряване на интермодалността, активната мобилност и модернизирание на данните и цифровата инфраструктура на града.
- Да се осигури управление на транспорта, основано на данни, за да се подпомогнат сезонните пикове в търсенето и да се повиши ефективността, устойчивостта и трайността на цялостната система за мобилност във Варна.

Подробности за случаите на употреба

Площ **238 КМ²**
Жители **323,000**

ВАРНА

Who?

- Жителите на Варна и местните търговски обекти
- Институционални и оперативни институции
- Местни компании, подпомагащи събирането на данни

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 12: Roll-ups for the local-kick-off meetings in pilot sites' languages (Bulgarian)

4.5.2 ARTICLES, PRESS RELEASES, POPULAR SCIENCE

The project will regularly publish accessible content to highlight milestones like pilot site updates, events, and major achievements. These materials will connect MODALSHIFT’s goals to broader themes such as environmental policies and innovative transport solutions. Contributions from experts will connect technical insights with environmental perspectives.

4.5.3 MODALSHIFT NEWSLETTER

During the project, a newsletter will be published every 6 months, starting at **M12** (May 2026). The overall objective is to give updates about the project to a larger audience than on social media. Aside from providing general updates about the project activities, it will allow readers to follow the deployment of the solutions by providing information about upcoming events organised by MODALSHIFT partners.

A subscription link to the newsletter is available on the MODALSHIFT website.

We expect the impact of the newsletter to be amplified by the sharing of the information provided through the MODALSHIFT newsletter via partners' existing newsletters. The partners that will share MODALSHIFT news through their own newsletters are the following:

Table 10: Partner's newsletter information

Partners	Newsletter	Frequency	Audience
ATOBE	The company's newsletter highlights innovation activities, research collaborations and participation in EU projects. Updates on mobility solutions and digital technologies included.	Every 6 months	Industry stakeholders, innovation networks, and the public.
AIT	Institute's newsletter featuring project updates, technological impacts and key institutional announcements.	Every 6 months	General public, research and innovation community.
TELLAE	The company's newsletter covering TELLAE's activities across different areas of work, with a focus on technology, R&D, and business applications.	Every month or every three months	General public and technological partners.
ITA	Actualities, technology news, articles about mobility, projects, success stories, and technological solutions.	Every 3 months	Providers, clients and customers in sustainable mobility.

4.5.4 WHITE PAPER & POLICY BRIEFS

AIT, together with technical and use case partners, will analyse policy developments at both national and EU levels that could support an optimised multimodal transport network connecting passenger and freight mobility, based on pilot site activities. ID4M and CS partners will suggest regulatory changes to establish technical requirements and social acceptance frameworks throughout the EU, promoting broader adoption. The team will also prepare a white paper containing recommendations for implementing multimodal network optimisation services targeted at local authorities (Deliverable D6.2 - Regulatory and policy recommendations), scheduled for Month 42 (November 2028). Additionally, AIT, ID4M, ITA, and IMEC will explore potential structural reforms needed to fully support and boost the sustainability and uptake of the project's outcomes. Three policy briefs will be issued by AIT to facilitate broad dissemination—particularly at mobility policy events—and will be compiled along with analysis results in Deliverable D6.2.

4.5.5 PEER-REVIEW PUBLICATIONS

During the project, gold open-access peer-reviewed publications are planned to be released in journals and magazines chosen to maximise their impact. Additionally, results will be shared on partners' websites and through project newsletters. The types of publications and the intended target journals are described in detail in Table 11.

Table 11: List of possible peer-reviewed journals targeted

Peer-reviewed journals targeted
European Transport Research Review

Transportation Research Part A
Transportation Research Part B https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/transportation-research-part-b-methodological
Transportation Research Part C https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/transportation-research-part-c-emerging-technologies
Transportation Research Part D https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/transportation-research-part-d-transport-and-environment
Transportation Research Part E https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/transportation-research-part-e-logistics-and-transportation-review
Transportation Research Part F https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/transportation-research-part-f-traffic-psychology-and-behaviour
Transport Reviews
Sustainability
Knowledge-Based Systems

4.5.6 CONFERENCE & EVENTS

4.5.6.1 Engagement workshops

MODALSHIFT will host events including, a project launch, thematic roundtables, and a final conference to bring together experts, policymakers, and community members to discuss sustainable mobility and modal shift challenges.

Engagement workshops with local stakeholders will also be organised at the case studies. Indeed, at least 3 local workshops organised with the participation of more than 5 members from the logistics and freight value chain stakeholders, and the mobility of people value chain stakeholders will be held. Participation in more than 5 events targeting Transport network stakeholders, local actors' boards involving more than 5 mobility users per pilot site, participation in at least 1 webinar organised in each pilot site language, are among the performance indicators required to ensure MODALSHIFT's sustainability (*cf. Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.*, Table 4, Table 5, **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**, Table 7. A summary of the communication campaign for TG5 is also included. , **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**).

4.5.6.2 External events

Participation in conferences will start from the second half of the project to present results. Table 12 below lists examples of events MODALSHIFT partners can participate in:

Table 12: List of potential events that MODALSHIFT partners can attend to or participate in

Event/conference name	Date/frequency	Upcoming location
Transport Research Arena (TRA)	18-21 May 2026/every two years	Budapest
ITS European Congress	27-29 April 2026/ every year	Istanbul
ITS World Congress	25-29 October 2027/every year	Birmingham
CCAM (RTR conference – Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility)	10-12 February 2026/ every year	Brussels
Urban Mobility Days (European Commission – DG MOVE)	30 September – 02 October 2025/ every two years	Vilnius

European Transport Conference (ETC)	17-19 September 2025/every year	Antwerp – Porto (2026)
UITP Global Public Transport Summit	21-23 April 2026/every two years	Dubai
ALICE Logistics Innovation Summit	23-24 October 2025/every year	Louvain-la-Neuve
Research group in Logistics and Supply Chain (ITA – ZLC - UNIZAR)	November 2025/every year research workshop	Zaragoza
Modelling World	17-18 June 2026/every year	Leeds
World conference on transport research (WCTR)	6-10 July 2026/every three years	Toulouse

4.5.7 NETWORKING AND SYNERGIES WITH JOINT INITIATIVES

MODALSHIFT will actively seek cooperation and knowledge exchange with past and ongoing European projects addressing multimodal traffic and network management, also ensuring continuity and complementarity within the Horizon Europe and H2020 transport research programs.

ID4M has already started to establish an Advisory and Replication Board (ARB), which reunited for the first time in October 2025. The ARB aims to disseminate the project results beyond demonstration sites and to get advice from external experts.

Building on the experience of projects such as FRONTIER, ORCHESTRA, TANGENT and DIT4Tram, MODALSHIFT will explore possible collaborations through joint workshops, exchange of methodological approaches and datasets, particularly regarding multimodal coordination and digital governance frameworks. Particular attention will be given to Horizon Europe projects funded under related topics, including DELPHI, SYNCHROMODE and AXUMEN, which share a focus on data-driven optimisation of multimodal transport systems. Especially, cooperation with the FEDORA project will be prioritised.

ID4M will lead the facilitation of a webinar at midterm, the participation in a POLIS conference and the writing of a collaborative white paper at the end of the project with the sisters' project (possibly in the scope of the Multimodal Traffic Management Cluster), ITA will lead the contributions of MODALSHIFT to the Digital Transport and Logistics Forum and the Common European Mobility Data Space initiatives, notably through the participation in their regular events and working groups, providing outcomes related to the use cases of MODALSHIFT. As chair of the Thematic Group "Traffic Management and Modelling", AIT will lead the collaboration with the European Conference of Transport Research Institutes. Partners will also be engaged in various communities (e.g. NGS with C-ITS, ADF in EU-Rail Joint Undertaking WG sharing its expertise and insights from MODALSHIFT and PNAEAS with Zero-Emission Waterborne Transport). The collaboration with INNOVEE, building on the recent inclusion of Canada in the Horizon Europe programme, will maximise the networking activities in Canada.

5 EXPLOITATION ACTIVITIES

5.1.1 EXPLOITATION STRATEGY

Developing an exploitation and post-project strategy is essential for the long-term impact of the MODALSHIFT initiative. Key aspects to be outlined include:

- Identification of project results suitable for exploitation ;
- Identification of which partners are responsible for exploiting each result and the overall technological solution (ITA);
- Specification of the technology's end-users (ITA);
- Adaptation of MODALSHIFT dynamic pricing models (ATOBE, AIT, ID4M, TELLAE, local partners) and data providers' engagement strategies to new contexts and generation of practical guidelines for adaptation.
- Identification of funding opportunities (EQY) that could support solution providers in the follow-up steps towards the upscale of their PR and KERs.

The MODALSHIFT consortium has identified 10 project results (PRs) / key exploitable results (KERs), detailed in Table 13 below, based on the degree of innovation, the exploitability and the impact.

Table 13: Key exploitation results of MODALSHIFT

KERs	Partners
Capacity-as-a-service design and strategies for increasing the value of multimodal transport services	ID4M, ADF, PNAEAS
Governance schemes, dynamic incentives and business models	ATOBE, AIT
Data collection and communication systems for infrastructures, vehicles, people and loads	NGS
Trusted and secure mobility and freight data spaces	ITA
Multimodal transport network digital twins in case studies.	ITA, GGI
Traffic forecasting algorithms	IMEC
Multi-objective decision-making algorithms for network and traffic management.	KEDGE, ITA, IMEC, AIT, TELLAE
Collaborative platform for multisource multistakeholder traffic and network management	ATOBE
Dynamic tools for daily transport service providers' operations	GGI, ATOBE
Data and scenario visualisation platform for the planning of transport modes and services	TELLAE, AIT

ITA will lead the development of an **Innovation Management Plan** released at M25 to the entire consortium that will be annually updated and finally integrated into the **D6.3 - Exploitation strategies and innovation landscape** at M38 (July 2028) by ID4M.

6 MANAGEMENT

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PROCEDURES

Based on the proposal, all partners are expected to contribute to leverage the visibility of any dissemination, communication and exploitation activities throughout the project lifetime. Even so, EQY is the leader of the Communication and Dissemination activities, while ID4M is handling the Exploitation-related activities; all partners have PMs involved in the tasks of the Work Package related to Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation tasks.

Based on their technical knowledge and pilot site handling, partners play a key role in the relevance of communication and dissemination activities by suggesting and implementing local communication and dissemination activities.

The present Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan will be updated during the project implementation, when relevant, and the objectives will be revised according to the progress.

IMPACT TRACKING AND MONITORING

All activities implemented by all partners throughout the project will be tracked in a document made by EQY for all partners on the SharePoint “the Communication and Dissemination tracker”. During the lifetime of the project, the partners will have to fill in according to their Comm&Diss’s activities agenda (publications, participations in and organisations of conferences and events, newsletters, articles, social media publications and the website content).

Communication and Dissemination activities impact evaluation will take place at every Consortium Meeting (every 6 months) and in more detail at each reporting period report. The evaluation will be made based on the following table summarising all communication & dissemination KPIs.

Table 14: Summary of Key Performance Indicators

Key Performance Indicator	Value
Conferences and events	
Number of conferences attended	>10
Number of events attended	>5
Number of local workshops organised	>6
Number of people in the target groups reached through the local workshop	>10
Number of webinars in each CS language organised	>3
Number of EU-wide webinars organised	>3
Number of CCAM event attendances	>2
Popular science articles and deliverables	
Number of popular science articles published	>6
Number of readers per article	>500
Number of scientific/technical papers in	>10
Number of joint papers in participation in	>4
Number of policy briefs and recommendations publicly available for participation	3
Number of policy-oriented journals in participation	>3
Number of views on public datasets/deliverables	>200
Online channel	
Number of visits to the website per year	>3000
Number of posts on social media per year	>20
Promotional material and visual identity	
Number of papers or digital brochures/leaflets distributed	>800
Number of views per video about the MODALSHIFT project	>2500

7 CONCLUSION

This DEC plan has as its main objective to ensure MODALSHIFT has the largest impact on the targeted stakeholders, audiences, and the general public (brand identity, communication materials, dissemination and communication agenda). It has been established to guide dissemination, exploitation and communication activities during the entire lifetime of the project. This DEC plan is based on a collaborative effort from all the partners to stimulate the public's interest in what will be achieved throughout the project.

This document remains changeable as the project is in its early stages. The adequacy of such a plan will be possible to leverage when the project is more advanced.